

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 05.03.2020 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Dr. Sham Kishore	Chairman
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Dr. Sukesh	Member
4. Dr. Pavanchand Attavar	Member
5. Dr. Vishrutha K V	Member
6. Ms. Shaik Farheen	Member
7. Ms. Kavya Shettigar K	Member
8. Mrs. Swathi Krishnan	Member
9. Mrs. Swathi D	Member
10. Mr. Devaseelan S	Member
11. Mrs. Laveena D'Souza	Member
12. Dr. Vrinda	Member
13. Ms. Sahana	Member
14. Mrs. Priyadhershini S	Member
15. Mrs. Shwetha B	Member

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 11.10.2019.
2. Approve finalized updates and changes for Academic Session 2018-19.
3. Discussion regarding addition of Few B.Sc. and M.Sc. Courses in the Academic Year 2020-21.
4. Revise Few Topics in the Course of 'Cardiac Care Technology'.
5. Discussion on Course name change of 'Respiratory Care Technology' to 'Respiratory Therapy'.

The Chairman Dr. Sham Kishore introduced himself, thanking and welcoming all the members who were present for the meeting. The meeting there after deliberated on agenda items as had been approved by the Chairman.

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 05.03.2020. As per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: The Finalized Updates and changes were proposed by the BOS for the Academic Session 2018-19 (Reference Page 3, Table 1) and had to be approved. Resolution was taken accordingly; updates and changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 3: The Discussion regarding the addition of few B.Sc. and M.Sc. Courses in Allied Health Science in the Academic Year 2020-21 was made and the same was approved by the BOS as suggested (Reference Table 2).

Agenda No. 4: To Revise the Topics of the course of ‘Cardiac Care Technology’ and Forensic Science’ was suggested by Dr. Sham Kishore and Sr. Faculty Shristina Subba. The syllabus was updated as per the suggestions mentioned by the stakeholders. The Revised Topics were confirmed and was approved by the BOS as suggested.

Agenda No. 5: The Discussion regarding the course name change was proposed regarding the ‘Respiratory Care Technology’ to ‘Respiratory Therapy’. The final decision was postponed to the next meeting.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Swathi D, Member, Board of Studies.

Dr. Sham Kishore,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Science

Table 1

Addition and Deletion in main subjects, subsidiary, topics in All Allied Health Courses

Course	Topics added/ deleted on BOS proposal	Reason
CCT	Addition: 5th semester: One subject name changed to approach to clinical cardiology	Subjects and topics are similar as Cardiovascular technology, but needs more clinical cardiology experience

Table 2

Courses approved for the academic year 2020-2021

Sl. No	Name of the Coursework
1.	B.Sc. Digital and Cyber Forensics
2.	B.Sc. Virology and Immunology
3.	B.Sc. Clinical Psychology
4.	B.Sc. Emergency Medicine
5.	B.Sc. Neuro Science
6.	B.Sc. Physician Assistant
7.	M.Sc. Criminology and Forensic Science
8.	M.Sc. Forensic Science
9.	M.Sc. Cyber security and Forensic Science
10.	M.Sc. Clinical Psychology
11.	M.Sc. Optometry

Members present:

Dr. Sham Kishore

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Dr. Sukesh

Dr. Pavanchand Attavar

Dr. Vishrutha K V

Ms. Shaik Farheen

Ms. Kavya Shettigar K

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